

October 31, 2021

Effect of Axillary Bud Suppression on Yield Attributes of Tomato

Author's Details:

Tabi kingsley Mbi^{1*}, Shuimuh Ezekiel Njodzeka¹, Tatah Eugene Lemzeyuy¹, Mendi Grace², Tamungang simon² and Chi Christopher Tamu³

⁽¹⁾Department of Crop Production Technology, College of Technology, University of Bamenda, Cameroon

⁽²⁾Department of Forestry and Wild life, College of Technology, University of Bamenda, Cameroon

⁽³⁾Department of Agricultural and Environmental Engineering, College of Technology, University of Bamenda, Cameroon

* Corresponding author: kingotabimbi@yahoo.com

Received Date: 26-Sep-2021

Accepted Date: 20-Oct-2021

Published Date: 31-Oct-2021

Abstract

This study was carried out to determine the effect of manual and chemical methods of axillary bud pruning on yield of tomato. Manual method of axillary bud pruning was mainly by nipping at different time intervals while chemical method involved treatment with Indole acetic acid (IAA) at different interval of application. The experiment was carried out in the experimental field of the Regional College of agriculture Bambili, North West Region of Cameroon. The experimental layout was a complete block design with the 3 main blocks being manual pruning by nipping, chemical pruning by IAA, and the control (zero pruning) repeated thrice. Results obtained revealed that both methods of axillary bud pruning improved fruit yield. Chemical method of axillary bud suppression through exogenous application of 100 μ M IAA at 7 days interval gave significantly higher fruit diameter, fruit weight and number of marketable fruits compared to the time consuming and laborious nipping method and the control.

Key words: Fruit yield, Indole acetic acid, Nipping, Pruning, Tomato

Abbreviations: IAA- Indole acetic acid

INTRODUCTION

Tomato is the most widely cultivated vegetable in Cameroon. Although, it is grown as a subsistence crop in all the five agro-ecological zones of the country, commercial fields are mostly found in the Western highlands, where climatic conditions are conducive for growing tomato (Temple, 2001). Bambili is one of the production hubs of tomato in the North West Regions of Cameroon. In spite of frantic efforts put in place by tomato farmers in this locality, small sizes of fruits remains a major hitch to 90 % growers. Small fruit may weigh less, have a shorter shelf life and reduced marketability. Small fruit sizes do not only reduce shelf life but worse still leads to loss of market value for tomatoes due to their low grade (Islam *et al.*, 2019). Among factors contributing to small sizes are unfavourable environmental conditions like low ambient-light conditions (Gruda, 2005), soil salinity, imbalance in soil nutrients (Islam *et al.*, 2018), water stress throughout the growing season (Nurrudin *et al.*, 2003) as well as overcrowding caused by poor agronomic practices. Besides the non respect of the normal planting distances, overcrowding in tomato farms is caused by development of axillary buds to lateral branches. Generally pruning is a plausible crop husbandry solution to problems related to overcrowding caused by full development of side shoots. Pruning is a crop management practice which involves the removal of non-productive parts like side shoots, extra flowers, fruits and diseased leaves in order to divert energy into those parts that are capable of bearing fruits. Pruning also helps to maintain a proper proportion of root/shoot ratio (Thakur *et al.*, 2018).

October 31, 2021

In tomato, pruning is mainly carried out manually with the use of the hand or a scissors to nip off the side shoots. The process is however painstaking and time consuming, probable reason why farmers are reluctant to put it into practice. Indole acetic acid (IAA) is a plant growth regulatory substance which has been reported to control side shoot development through the concept of apical dominance. Apical dominance is the control exerted by the shoot apex over the outgrowth of the lateral buds. Thimann and Skoog (1933) first demonstrated the role of auxin in apical dominance as they removed the shoot apex of the herbaceous species *Vicia faba* and repressed subsequent lateral bud outgrowth by application of auxin to the top of the decapitated stem. This classical auxin replacement experiment works in many herbaceous plants (Cline, 2000), and it is commonly cited as evidence for a repressive role of apically produced auxin in the control of lateral bud growth in apical dominance. Evidence on the repressive role of auxin led to the assumption that exogenous auxin application could be a potential method of controlling axillary bud growth in tomato. It was within this context that, this study was carried out with the objective to evaluate the impact of axillary bud suppression by auxin on yield of tomato.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out on the experimental farm of the Regional College of Agriculture Bambui, from July – November 2020. Bambili is a town in the North West Region of Cameroon, with geographical location, located 5° 59 '0" North and 10° 15' 0" east and 2273m above sea level. Temperatures range from 13°C to 18°C, annual rainfall of 2125mm, and atmospheric pressure of 1012hpa and air humidity of 85%. The area has two seasons, the rainy season which is the longest and starts from mid-March to mid-November and the dry season from mid November to March.

Nursery

Dark soil rich in humus was collected from a backyard garden and sterilized by heating in a pot. The next day, the soil was mixed with poultry manure at a ratio of 3:1 V/V and filled into polybags of 100 ml volume and suspended on a wooden surface. Two Seeds of Nadira F1 tomato purchased from the farmers shop were carefully placed in holes at depth of 2 cm. The nursery was watered well and the watering continued daily until the seeds broke dormancy. Watering was done every day at 5:00 PM and 7 days later the seeds germinated. Thinning was done after one week and seedlings were allowed in the nursery for one month. A week before transplanting, the seedlings were hardened by reducing shade and frequency of watering.

Land preparation

Two weeks to transplanting, the experimental field was first sprayed with systemic herbicide (supper killer). Following the dead of the grasses, clearing and tilling was done and beds arranged according to the experimental layout. Holes for the tomato were dug and well decomposed fowl manure applied by sporting. Two days later, the tomato seedlings were transplanted by simply removing the polybag and the intact substrate lowered into the 10 cm deep holes.

Crop management

Two weeks after transplanting, first fertilizer (NPK 20:10:10) was applied followed by first moulding. Two weeks later folia fertilizer (Ferti flora and Ferti Production) was applied to boost vegetative growth. To control pest and diseases the plants were sprayed twice a week with fungicide (pencozeb and Fungi champ) to prevent fungi infection in the farm and insecticide (fighter) to check insect attack. Staking was done after 7 weeks. The dry season came earlier than expected hence a watering can as used to irrigate the field once every 72 hours. Weeding was done manually at the end of every third week.

Preparation of Indole III acetic acid (IAA) stock and working solution

A 0.01M stock solution of IAA was prepared by weighing 0.8875g of IAA on an electronic balance, dissolved in 6ml ethanol in a beaker and water added to the 500ml level. The stock solution was then stored in a refrigerator at temperature of 4°C. Prior to each spraying day, a working solution was prepared from the stock solution using the dilution equation

October 31, 2021

$$C_1V_1 = C_2V_2$$

Where C_1 =concentration of stock solution (0.1M)

V1=volume of stock solution

C2=Concentration of working solution (100 μ M)

V2=Volume of working solution (1L)

The working solution was then used to spray the respective sub plots at intervals of 7days, 14days and 21days. IAA treatment started 2 weeks after transplanting.

Experimental design

During tilling, beds were arranged in a complete split plot experimental design in a 3 x 3 x 20 layout. The main plots were the 3 methods of pruning (no pruning or control, nipping, and chemical pruning) while the sub plots were the intervals of nipping (7days, 14days and 21days) and chemical treatments (7days, 14days and 21days), and each sub plot made up of 20 plants.

As regards mechanical pruning, the method adopted was two stem. Nipping was done to retain only two main stems. All the buds that developed below were systematically nipped with the hand.

Data collection and analysis

The parameters studied included the mean number of truss/plant, number of opened flowers/truss and number of fruits/truss. The mean fruits diameter/plant was gotten by measuring the diameter of the biggest and smallest fruit from all the trusses on the plant. Mean fruit weight was also taken. Finally the number of marketable size fruits was determined. A fruit was considered marketable if its diameter is $\geq 1/4$ the largest fruit. The data collected were subject to the analysis of Variance using a statistical package SPSS version 22. The means of treatments were separated using LSD at the P=0.05 level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Shoot branching is the process by which axillary buds, located on the axil of a leaf, develop and form new flowers or branches (Ongaro and Leyser, 2008). During shoot branching, the axillary meristem in the leaf axils is activated, leading to the generation of a lateral branch (New *et al.*, 2015). Full development of axillary buds into lateral branching has been reported to affect plant growth and crop productivity (Barbier *et al.*, 2019). The process by which a dormant bud activates and becomes an actively growing branch is complex and very finely tuned (Ongaro and Leyser, 2008). Tomato has sympodial shoot architecture with determinate or indeterminate growth habits as well as bushy lateral branches phenotype. Controlling the level of branching by pruning is a crop husbandry operation to enhance yields. Pruning involves the selective removal of side shoots or stem aimed at limiting vegetative growth and to divert nutrients to flower clusters and fruit development on the remaining shoot or stem (Alam *et al.*, 2016). In the present study, pruning of lateral branches greatly influenced reproductive parameters of tomato.

The control plot scored a significantly higher number of trusses than the two methods of axillary bud pruning (Figure 1). Though the control recorded a higher number of trusses, no significant differences were observed at the level of anthesis between the control and the treatments (Figure 2). The control plot however failed to maintain the level of significance as far as fruit development parameters (Figure 3, 4, 5) were concerned.

October 31, 2021

* Different letters on bars indicate significant difference at $p \leq 0.05$

Figure 1. Influence of axillary bud suppression on number of trusses produced/plant

In spite of the significant number of trusses produced in the control plots over plots treated with bud suppression by nipping and IAA (figure 1), no significant differences were observed for mean number of flowers that attained anthesis (Figure 2) and average number of fruits set/truss (Figure 3) in all plots. This is an indication that most of the flowers in the control plots failed to bloom and did not set fruits.

* Different letters on bars indicate significant difference at $p \leq 0.05$

Figure 2. Influence of axillary bud suppression on anthesis

October 31, 2021

As regards further developmental parameters like mean fruit diameter (Figure 4), mean fruit weight per plant (Figure 5) and number of marketable fruits (Figure 6), plants under different intervals of nipping and IAA treatments, scored highly significant differences while the least scores were recorded in the control plot. Highly significant results were scored for tomato plots subjected under pruning by nipping and IAA methods of axillary bud suppression compared to the control plot. The results are in accord with the findings of Gong *et al.* (2019) which showed that excess of lateral branches due to non pruning operation have negative influences on tomato yield. When all lateral bud in tomatoes are allowed to develop, there is overcrowding and the developing fruits in the various trusses are pruned to competition for resources like nutrient allocation and light harvesting during photosynthesis. This probably explains the reasons why fruit yield parameters were significantly greater in plots there were under pruning compared to non pruned plots. In addition, overcrowding in tomato farms favours disease incidence and severity especially in lower leaves which in turn reduces yields (Navarrete *et al.*, 2000; Gong *et al.*, 2019). Generally each developed lateral branch produces its own trusses leading to many trusses than the plant can support. An increase in the number of trusses means an increase in the number of sinks for storage of photosynthate hence competition sets in and further fruit development is limited as observed in Figure 1. The end result is of course small size fruits which reduces the grade as well as marketability of the fruits. This has been shown clearly in the results of the present study as the fruit diameter (Figure 4), weight (Figure 5) and total numbers of marketable fruits (Figure 6) scores are highly significant in plots treated with IAA and nipping compared to the control.

* Different letters on bars indicate significant difference at $p \leq 0.05$

Figure 3. Influence of axillary bud suppression on fruit set

October 31, 2021

* Different letters on bars indicate significant difference at $p \leq 0.05$

Figure 4. Influence of axillary bud suppression on fruit size

* Different letters on bars indicate significant difference at $p \leq 0.05$

Figure 5. Influence of axillary bud suppression on fruit weight

October 31, 2021

* Different letters on bars indicate significant difference at $p \leq 0.05$

Figure 6. Influence of axillary bud suppression on number of marketable fruits

Although the two methods of pruning improved on fruit yield parameters, plots treated with IAA scored significantly important yields than plots under nipping (Figure 4, 5 and 6). Similar results had been reported by Ranin (2003) who reported an increase in fruit size and number of marketable fruits in tomato plants treated with auxin. Ahmed (2013) also reported an increase in fruit length, diameter and weight and a drop in fruit drop in dates plants treated with IAA. Lateral bud outgrowth is mainly controlled by apical dominance and the crosstalk between the plant hormones auxin, cytokinin and strigolactone, a novel long distance carotenoid derived signal which acts as a branching inhibitor (Rameau, 2010). Bud outgrowth is not regulated only by hormones but by the interaction of environmental and endogenous signals i.e. plant hormones. Auxin is actively transported basipetally in the shoot and inhibits bud outgrowth (Ongaro and Leyser, 2008). This implies that development of any axillary bud depends on its distance from the shoot tip. Thus the further the axillary bud is away from the shoot tip, the lesser the influence of auxin and the more its development into a full branch. This probably explains why exogenous treatment with IAA in the present study suppressed even the furthest axillary buds from growing into full branches. The overall significance of IAA compared to nipping might also be attributed to the fact that auxin is involved in many developmental processes in plants among which are seed development and grain yield (Cao *et al.*, 2020), fruit development including fruit set, growth, ripening and abscission (Pattison *et al.*, 2014, de Jong *et al.*, 2009). Parthenocarpy, which is the ability to bypass pollination to form fruits has also been reported in tomato in the presence of a high concentration auxin (Serrani *et al.*, 2008), this too could be a contributing factor why exogenous application IAA led to improvement in number of fruits per plant as well as marketable fruits.

Though nipping had a significance influence on yield parameters compared to non pruned plot, the process is associated with some inconveniences to both the plant and farmer. The major inconvenience of nipping to the plant is the stress to heal wounds created given that wounds might act as entry points to pests and some pathogens. To the farmer, the process of nipping is laborious and painstaking compared to treatment with IAA. Nevertheless limiting the frequency of nipping to 14 days will not only limit the stress undergone by the plant but also reduces labour intensity.

CONCLUSION

In this research the importance of axillary bud suppression was clearly demonstrated as

October 31, 2021

1. Chemical pruning using indole III acetic acid gave better tomato yield in terms of number of fruits, fruit diameter, number of marketable fruits compared to manual pruning by nipping and zero pruning.
2. Manual pruning by nipping at 14 days interval gave better yields compared to zero pruning.
3. Over all, the use of IAA at concentration of 100uM at 7 days interval to reduce axillary bud growth proves to be the best option owing to its advantages over nipping in terms of time, labour and other developmental influences on vegetative and reproductive growth in the crop.

Acknowledgement

The authors appreciate material support from the Regional College of Agriculture Bambili, North West Region of Cameroon.

REFERENCES

- i. Ahmed, S., Sajid, M., Latif, A., Ahmed, N., Junaid, M., Mahmood, N. and Umair M. (2013). *Effect of indole acetic acid (IAA) on fruit drop and fruit quality of date palm cultivars*. International Journal of Pure and Applied Bioscience 2: 1-6.
- ii. Alam, M.S., Islam, N., Ahmad, S., Hossen, M.I. and Islam, M.R. (2016). *Effect of different staking methods and stem pruning on yield and quality of summer tomato*. Bangladesh Journal of Agricultural Research 41: 419-432.
- iii. Barbier FF, Dun EA, Kerr SC, Chabikwa TG, Beveridge CA. (2019). *An update on the signals controlling shoot branching*. Trends Plant Science 24: 220-236.
- iv. Cao, J., Li, G., Qu, D., Li, X. and Wang, Y. (2020). *Into the Seed: Auxin Controls Seed Development and Grain Yield*. International Journal of Molecular Science 21, 1662;
- v. Cline, M.G. (2000). *Execution of the auxin replacement apical dominance experiment in temperate woody species*. American Journal of Botany 87: 182–190.
- vi. de Jong, M., Wolters-Arts, M., Feron, R., Mariani, C. and Vriezen, W.H. (2009). *The Solanum lycopersicum auxin response factor 7 (SlARF7) regulates auxin signaling during tomato fruit set and development*. Plant Journal 57: 160 – 170.
- vii. Gong, B., Yan, Y., Zhang, L., Cheng, F., Liu, Z. and Shi Q. (2019). *Unravelling GSNOR-mediated S-nitrosylation and multiple developmental programmes in tomato plants*. Plant Cell Physiology 60: 2523-2537.
- viii. Gruda, N. (2005). *Impact of environmental factors on product quality of greenhouse vegetables for fresh consumption*. Critical Review in Plant Science 24: 227–247.
- ix. Islam, M.Z., Lee, Y.T., Mele, M.A., Choi, I.L. and Kang, H.M. (2019). *Effect of fruit size on fruit quality, shelf life and microbial activity in cherry tomatoes*. AIMS Agriculture and food 4: 340-348.
- x. Islam, M.Z, Mele, M.A., Choi, K.Y. and Kang M.H. (2018). *The effect of silicon and boron foliar application on the quality and shelf life of cherry tomatoes*. Zemdirbyste-Agriculture 105: 159–164.
- xi. New Lee., O, Uchida, Y., Nemoto, K., Mine, Y. and Sugiyama N. (2015). *Quantitative trait loci analysis of lateral shoot growth in tomato*. Scientia horticulturae 192: 117-124.
- xii. Nurrudin, M.M., Chandra, A.M. and Georges, T.D. (2003). *Effect of water stress on different growth stages on greenhouse tomato yield and quality*. Horticultural science 38: 1389–1393.
- xiii. Ongaro, V. and Leyser, O. (2008). *Hormonal control of shoot branching*. Journal of Experimental Botany 59: 67-74.
- xiv. Pattison, J.R., Csukaci, F. and Catala, C. (2014). *Mechanisms regulating auxin action during fruit development*. Physiologia Plantarum 151: 62 – 72.
- xv. Rameau, C. (2010). *Strigolactones, a novel class of plant hormone controlling shoot branching*. Comptes Rendus Biologies 333: 344 - 349.
- xvi. Ranin, A.A. (2003). *Effects of auxin application on fruit formation in tomato growing under stress temperatures in the field*. The journal of horticultural science 5: 706-710.

October 31, 2021

- xvii. *Serrani, J.C., Ruiz-Rivero, O., Fos, M. and Garcia-Martinez, J.L. (2008). Auxin-induced fruit-set in tomato is mediated in part by gibberellins. Plant Journal 56: 922 – 934.*
- xviii. *Temple, L. (2001). Quantification des productions et des échanges de fruits et légumes au Cameroun. Cahiers Agricultures 10: 87-94.*
- xix. *Thakur, O., Vijay, K. and Jitendra, S. (2018). A Review on Advances in Pruning to Vegetable Crops. International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences 7: 3556-3565.*
- xx. *Thimann KV, Skoog F. (1933). Studies on the growth hormones of plants. III. The inhibition action of growth substance on bud development. USA National Academy of Science Proceedings 19: 714 - 716.*